

THEORETICAL BASIS OF STUDYING ECONOMIC COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the theoretical foundations of studying the economic competence of future educators.*

Keywords: *competence, private property, entrepreneurship, interpersonal relations, behavior, behavior.*

In the world, it is considered necessary to create pedagogical and psychological mechanisms aimed at developing economic competences in future educators, providing a stable way of life for people, increasing the sense of responsibility in interpersonal relations, and forming personal and professional competences in the economy. According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2022/23 (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, GEM), the role of business and private entrepreneurship in solving social and economic problems in the world is increasing. According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitoring report, more than 11.5 million business entities are currently operating in the world. This not only greatly contributes to increasing the stability of the world's socio-economic development, but also requires more future teachers to have the ability to adapt and quickly respond to difficulties. From this point of view, the research of pedagogical-psychological adaptation, which plays an important role in the development of economic competences in future educators, and the development of the psychology of future educators remains one of the urgent problems.

In our country, as part of the reforms aimed at human interests, special attention is paid to the development of private property and entrepreneurship, a new economic outlook, and improvement of the psychological mechanisms of successful adaptation to market relations in order to ensure the effectiveness of entrepreneurial activities. Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev, while thinking about the priority tasks facing today's New Uzbekistan, including the real sector of the economy: "It should be noted separately that New Uzbekistan relies on a modernized economy. To form such an economy, it is necessary to continue institutional and structural reforms aimed at reducing the participation of the state in it, protecting the rights of private property and strengthening its role, stimulating the development of personal business and private entrepreneurship" [1].

Based on extensive psychological literature, the main reason why a person is called a product of social relations is that he is always surrounded by people and interacts with them. This indicates that one of the most leading and influential activities of a person is communication. Every normal person imagines himself as having the innate ability to listen to others, to convey his thoughts to others, that is, to speak, sometimes to express his thoughts in writing. But the ability to understand others and convey our thoughts and ideas to others means that we are in the system of human relations, that each of us cannot exist without a human society similar to us.]The study of interpersonal relations is one of the most urgent problems in psychology. Because communication, which is one of the most influential and leading activities of the human personality, and mutual relations through it, lead to the emergence of qualities such as

commonality, similarity, and harmony among people. Especially in the market environment, the specific aspects of interpersonal relations, such as between the producer and the consumer or the seller and the buyer, have a direct impact on the effectiveness and content of the person's life and activities. Therefore, the issue of studying interpersonal relations between people and their various psychological characteristics is one of the most important and urgent problems in the science of social psychology.

Communication is a form of interpersonal relations, with the help of which people enter into psychological contact with each other, exchange information, influence, be affected, perceive, understand and evaluate processes. Therefore, treatment is a socio-psychological phenomenon, a social category that directly participates in all spheres of social life and arises as an objective and subjective need that reflects the material, spiritual, emotional, cognitive, motivational, and regulatory aspects of cooperative activity. acts as the main factor, the basis.

L.S.Vygotsky points out that the main weapon and tool in interpersonal relations is the process of communication. In his opinion, in interpersonal relations, first, communication is the main tool, and then behavior is the tool. Because a person retains the function of communication even when he is alone.

Another aspect of the scientist's views is that behavior is manifested in the forms of behavior in the form of internalization (inner speech) and externalization (external speech). It can be seen that due to the transaction, the basis of the "seller-buyer" system of relations is created in society.

In general, L.S.Vygotsky's thoughts on the psychology of communication and interpersonal relations are extremely valuable, because in it we see communication as an important basis for the process of interaction of the "seller-buyer", and once again managed to understand that the value of this process in the formation of market relations is infinite [2].

Russian scientist V.M.Bekhterev [3] studied the problem of interpersonal relations, in particular, the subject of treatment in the context of his "Social-psychological concept". In the views of the scientist, the interaction of people is interpreted as an important problem. He describes the role of communication in social life and interprets its functions as a mechanism of cooperation. In his opinion, the more varied and rich the interaction of a person with others, the more successful his development [3].

V.M.Bekhterev in analyzing the social role and function of behavior, focuses on the significance of its manifestations, i.e., imitation and influence. In his opinion, if there was no imitation, there would be no personality. Because imitation means that it takes its material out of circulation. In the conclusions, influence is recognized as a factor of manifestation of social processes.

The scientist conditionally divides communication into direct and indirect types. If it takes a letter, telephone, telegram, caressing, fighting, etc. as components of indirect communication, it includes speech in the type of direct communication. Initially by V.M.Bekhterev was implemented it is worth noting that the study of behavior experimentally [3].

According to V.N.Myasishev's 4 concept of "Psychology of Relationships", a person has a "dialogic" character, manifests as a product of personal experience of dealings and interactions with other people. Due to this, a person has the internal power that drives a person, such as the level of interest, emotional strength, desire, desire, social orientation, and this is expressed in his experiences, behavior, and actions. Relation, in his words, "objectivity is the truly existing

interrelationship between humanity and existence. But it is subjective at the same time, because it belongs to humanity and the owner of the activity, and it is subjectively reflected in his mind.

Also V.N.Myasishchev according to, all mental phenomena can be considered in psychological analysis in the context of two categories - level (latent) and process (active) [4].

B.G.Ananov [5] in his work "Man as a subject of knowledge": "Human behavior is not only manifested as a complex set of his social activities, but with its help, his practical relationship with people of various social structures around him is also determined", he says.

According to B.F.Lomov [6], interpersonal interaction is manifested as an independent and unique form of subject activity.

In our opinion, communication and mutual understanding skills are very important in forming and improving economic competencies for future teachers. Also, through the use of interactive and practical approaches, analysis of real economic situations, participation in economic decision-making and problem solving, economic literacy of future educators will develop to a certain extent.

Today, against the background of economic and cultural reforms in our country, it is of particular importance to know the psychological conditions that ensure the effectiveness of interpersonal relations. In this case, mutual relations cover all areas of human life and serve as one of the necessary conditions for changing the individual and society as a whole. Several of our foreign and local scientists have conducted scientific research within the framework of this problem. For example, G.M.Andreeva, A.A.Bodalev, A.A.Brudniy, L.P.Bueva, Yu.N.Yemelyanov, A.G.Kovalev, A.A.Leontev, B.F.Lomov, G.Marcel, L.B.Filonov, R.Shovin, L.L.Yakubinsky, M.G.Davletshin, E.G.Ozиеv, V.M.Karimova, G.B.Shoumarov, Sh.R.Barotov, N.S.Safaev, U.D.Kadirov, O.E.Hayitov and others can be specially recognized.

Three types of tasks and a complex process structure that arise in interpersonal relations are described by G.M.Andreeva offers this structure in her book "Social Psychology":

- the communicative side of communication, i.e. as a process of interaction or exchange of information between participants in communication;

- the interactive side of communication, i.e. as a process of influencing the behavior of those who enter into communication;

- the perceptive side of communication, that is, as a process related to the perception and understanding of the participants of the communication B.F.Parigin that communication in relationships is psychologically complex. writes: "Communication is so multifaceted that it simultaneously includes the following processes:

- the process of interaction of individuals;
- the process of information exchange between individuals;
- the process of one person's relationship with another person;
- the process of one person influencing others;
- the opportunity to express sympathy to each other;
- the process of mutual understanding of individuals" [7].

The main goals of the parties entering into a relationship are to get along and understand each other. The complexity, if necessary, the "charm" and uniqueness of this process is that it is impossible for the parties to agree or think and speak exactly the same way. If we were to imagine such a situation, such communication would be the most ineffective and ineffective. For example, imagine that you went shopping at a store near your home. You asked the seller for the price of

the necessary goods, but he gave you the initiative and, no matter what you say, approves of you because of the price increase and retracts your statement. This interaction was very awkward, and you would have walked out of the store after dealing with the salesperson as formally as possible the second time around. That is, the activity of communication is such a condition that the individuality, uniqueness, variety of knowledge and imagination of each person is manifested in it, and thus it attracts mankind for centuries.

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